

D6.2 Business models for 5G-enabled Automotive service provisioning

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
5GAA	5G Automotive Association
6G-IA	6G Infrastructure Association
AF	Application Function
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOEP	Automotive Open Experimental Platform
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Customer
B2B2C	Business to Business to Customer
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DML	Distributed Machine Learning
EaaS	Experimentation as a Service
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FDD	Frequency Division Duplex
HD	High Definition
HW	Hardware
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
ISP	Internet Service Provider
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

Abbreviation	Definition
LTE	Long Term Evolution
ML	Machine Learning
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MVNO	Mobile Virtual Network Operator
NF	Network Function
NSA	Non-Stand Alone
OBU	On Board Unit
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
OTT	Over The Top
PPDR	Public Protection and Disaster Relief
PPP	Private Public Partnership
PSAP	Public Safety Answering Point
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
RSU	Road Side Unit
SA	Stand Alone
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SDN	Software Defined Network
SIM	Subscriber Identity Module
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SW	Software
TETRA	TErrestrial Trunked RAdio
UC	Use Case

Abbreviation	Definition
V2N	Vehicle to Network
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle to everything
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

5G-IANA aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third party experimenters, in the Automotive-related vertical can have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. This deliverable provides details on the business models associated with the development and provision of automotive services using the 5G-IANA platform as example. The discussion initiated here can be used for other experimentation platforms that have similar characteristics.

The main challenges that are related with the provisioning of services in the automotive vertical are discussed. These include the deployment of 5G networks, which will provide the end user with connectivity, issues regarding charging based on QoS, and cross border connectivity continuation. Several scenarios for the service creation and provision showing the different roles that actors can take within the ecosystem are presented and discussed considering the ecosystem around the 5G-IANA experimentation platform. The dominant role of the Mobile Network Operator (MNO) in all the scenarios is highlighted. Scenarios where all actors have discrete roles or cooperate are also presented. The indicative scenarios of 5G service provisioning that are presented include individual developers that provide their services through a marketplace, a vehicle manufacturer that leases slices with different requirements from an MNO and the provisioning of services within a private network.

More details on aspects of the initial business models that were introduced in D6.1: *Market analysis and initial business models*, related to the service provisioning for third parties of the 5G-IANA AOEP, are presented. The main 5G-IANA service is the experimentation on the platform using all available resources. A set of additional value-added services that are associated with the experimentation will be offered, i.e., support on how to use the platform, targeted training on the platform functionalities and consulting service that include both technical and business mentoring. The main cost categories associated with the provisioning of the services are defined. An analysis of the different type of revenues and service bundles that can be created is also presented. This analysis is crucial for the upcoming activities within WP6 that are related to the techno-economic analysis and the sustainability analysis of the 5G-IANA platform that will be presented in D6.4 at the end of the project.

Finally, the business models for the UCs are presented. Information regarding the targeted market, the involved stakeholders, the main costs and revenues sources along with a Lean Canvas for all UCs are presented.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. 5G-IANA concept and approach

5G-IANA aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third party experimenters, i.e., Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Automotive-related 5G-PPP vertical will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. An Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP) will be specified, as the whole set of hardware and software resources that provides the computational and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced nApp Toolkit tailored to the Automotive sector. 5G-IANA will expose to experimenters secured and standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for facilitating all the different steps towards the production stage of a new service. 5G-IANA targets different virtualization technologies integrating different Management and Orchestration (MANO) frameworks for enabling the deployment of the end-to-end network services across different domains (vehicles, road infrastructure, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) nodes and cloud resources). 5G-IANA nApp toolkit is linked with a new Automotive Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) Repository including an extended list of ready to use open accessible Automotive-related VNFs and nApp templates, that provides a repository for SMEs to use and develop new applications. Finally, 5G-IANA develops a Distributed Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning (AI/ML) (DML) framework, that will provide functionalities for simplified management and orchestration of collections of AI/ML service components and will allow ML-based applications to penetrate the Automotive world, due to its inherent privacy preserving nature. 5G-IANA will be demonstrated through 7 Automotive-related use cases in two 5G Stand Alone (SA) testbeds. Moving beyond technological challenges, and exploiting input from the demonstration activities, 5G-IANA performs a multi-stakeholder cost-benefit analysis that will identify and validate market conditions for innovative, yet sustainable business models supporting a long-term roadmap towards the pan-European deployment of 5G as key advanced Automotive services enabler.

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The objective of the deliverable is to present the work performed under T6.3: Sustainable business models. The main challenges that are related to the provisioning of the new automotive services on top of the 5G System are discussed and different scenarios that each actor can take within the ecosystem are presented.

The deliverable takes the business models for the 5G-IANA platform that were developed in D6.1: *Market analysis and initial business models* [1] and provides more details about the services that can be provided, the cost structure and the foreseen type of revenues. The development of the business models of the different UCs is also presented.

The information in this deliverable is required for the development of the sustainability analysis that will be reported in *D6.4: Techno-economic analysis and sustainability of 5G-IANA business models*. The final business model for the 5G-IANA platform and the UCs will be updated also in this deliverable.

The deliverable is structured as follows: in section 2 the main challenges for 5G service provisioning are presented along with different scenarios regarding the roles that the main actors can take within the ecosystem. Chapter 3 provides more details about the business model envisioned for the 5G-IANA AOEP platform while chapter 4 focuses on the business models of the seven UCs that are developed in the project.

The scope of the deliverable has been reoriented as per the project's interim review (June 2022), so as include in addition to the business models of the UCs the business model for the 5G-IANA AOEP platform.

1.3. Intended audience

The dissemination level of D6.2 is 'public' (PU) so is available to members of the consortium, the European Commission (EC) Services and all interested parties external to the Project. This document is intended to serve as a guideline and reference for all 5G-IANA beneficiaries about the foreseen business model of the 5G-IANA platform and the business models of the developed UCs. The information can be also used by facilitators of similar experimental platforms. Third parties can use the document to learn more about the developed business model of the use cases as examples that can be adopted for their products or services.

2. CREATION AND PROVISIONING OF AUTOMOTIVE SERVICES ON 5G NETWORKS

This section presents different aspects related to the creation and provisioning of 5G automotive services on top of the 5G network. Initially an overview of the main challenges is presented, followed by different models that can be used for the service creation and provisioning. Different scenarios are discussed, and their value networks are created using the roles and the reference model that were introduced in D6.1.

2.1. Challenges for 5G service provisioning

Although we envision the creation of new services that will utilize the potential of 5G networks, there are yet a couple of challenges that must be addressed. 5G networks are already deployed in several countries but until now most of these are based on the Non-Standalone Architecture (NSA) which enables mobile operators to reuse their 4G network infrastructure and to gradually migrate to the 5G Standalone Architecture (SA). The situation differs in private networks where most of them are deployed with SA from the beginning. Only 5G SA allows to fully exploit the potential of the new mobile standard, such as network slicing. The 5G roll-out cost is very high especially if both national coverage is targeted as well as increasing the radio capacity in areas with high population density to support a wide range of diverse services. Deployment of 5G networks in underserved areas also poses challenges to operators since the backhauling must be supported by fiber networks that are typically absent in rural environments. For automotive vertical, it is of importance that major transport routes are served by 5G. Similarly, continuous service operation when crossing borders is critical. Although the coverage of 5G networks is increasing, until now the main developments are the increased connection rates that in most of the cases are not easily perceived by users since the applications that take full potential of the new 5G enhancements (such as low latency) are still in preliminary stage.

MNOs are eager to find alternative sources of revenues. They are beginning to realize that there can be more opportunities in the B2B market and are shifting their interest in this part of the market. They are already deploying private networks for industrial partners mainly for manufacturing cooperations. For example, in USA, the Department of Defence is one of the largest end-users of 5G services [2].

The willingness to pay for the new technology is still uncertain in most cases as end-users are not familiar with concrete examples of what the new technology can offer to them. A coordinated approach is needed among MNOs, public and government institutions and all relevant stakeholders in order to facilitate the uptake of 5G, especially in the different Verticals. One of the solutions that is emerging in most of the countries is the creation of places like living labs where service developers and researchers can experiment and interact with MNOs and other stakeholders in an effort to build and expand the 5G ecosystem. These living labs are created by MNOs in collaboration with equipment vendors in order to trial and demonstrate various aspects of 5G. For example, only in EU, more than 260 of these efforts have been identified until the end of 2021 [4]. In most of the cases, these are closed with no opportunity for third parties to participate. Another option that is seen is the creation of experimentation platforms, usually with the collaboration of academia, research centers, equipment vendors and MNOs. In these cases, the labs are used for test purposes and members of the research community have the opportunity to perform their experiments. There are also Government funded initiatives [5] to build living labs in different verticals in order to identify new use cases and success stories. What is lacking from all these initiatives is the lack of open experimentation platforms that service developers and SMEs can access, perform their experiments and create their services. That was timely understood by the EU that initially funded a number of projects under the ICT-41 [6] call (5G-IANA is among the ones that are funded under this call).

The main advantages of experimentation platforms and living labs can be summarized to the following:

- Allow new actors to enter the 5G ecosystem.
- Increase the creation of new 5G services.
- Create a place where the different stakeholders can interact and exchange ideas.
- Promote the sharing of resources among the stakeholders.
- Create a repository of services and good practices.
- Help in the training and acquisition of new skills.

The following section provides an overview of the main challenges that are related to the mass adoption of 5G services. Some of them are related only to the automotive vertical that the 5G-IANA platform is the main target, but most of these challenges are more general and are related to the general adoption of 5G services.

2.1.1. 5G deployment

The main issue that MNOs are facing is the increased cost of installing the new equipment considering the uncertainty on consumers' and business' willingness to pay for the new technology. Deployment of 5G in almost all countries (at least where there is an extended incumbent 4G network) is based on a gradual evolution of the 4G network. In most of the countries, the approach that is used is to first implement a 5G NSA network and evolve it to 5G SA. Utilisation of existing 4G macro-cells is a solution that is exploited to mitigate some of these costs, leveraging the capabilities of macro-cells that provide superior coverage. In the future, increased capacity demand, along with restrictions on radio wave exposure, will make the installation of cells with smaller coverage radius necessary, while one of the main issues that arises is that especially in Dense Urban European cities the space for installing new equipment is limited. Independent of the deployment approach that operators have adopted, what is certain is that new investments are required to densify the network in areas with high population density and provide the higher QoS that 5G promises.

Regarding deployment, the three main business models that are foreseen are the following:

- Each MNO builds its own network. It is the traditional model that MNOs have followed for the deployment of their networks and the evolution from one generation to the next (for example from 3G to 4G). MNOs make all the investments and own the whole infrastructure.
- A group of MNOs build a common infrastructure or divide geographically the country into lots where each of them deploys the infrastructure and then they share the network having signed multilateral sharing agreements. In this case another option is to also use network resources from local operators or even private networks that wish to join this effort (in case these exist). The advantage is that some of the costs are shared among the operators and the deployment speed can be increased compared to the previous case, but there are issues that must be clarified such as the charging principles, who gets priority in accessing the resources in case there is a high demand, etc.
- The Neutral Host model in which an entity takes the role of building a single network, owns the infrastructure and provides wholesale service under the same conditions to all interested parties. It provides certain advantages especially in

areas with high population density. The utilisation of SDN and slicing makes possible for the service providers to individually manage their allocated resources and achieve a flexibility that is not possible with traditional ways of infrastructure sharing that was used until now.

Network sharing has been identified as an efficient way for the deployment of network in several projects as for example 5GCAR [7] and 5GMobix [8] and the 5G PPP Automotive Working Group [9] while the Neutral Host model has been studied in 5GCity [10].

Sharing agreements seem to be the most promising since they lower both CAPEX and OPEX, while at the same time it will be difficult especially in Dense Urban areas where the densification of the network will first begin to find space and equipment to install parallel networks for each of the operators (that have fiber and power connectivity). Especially for these areas the neutral host model seems the most promising and is already partially adopted by companies that own cell towers and other equipment.

Although network sharing has certain advantages, it also presents issues that must be addressed, which are mostly related to accountability issues related to network performance and availability. For example, the question arises regarding who is responsible in cases of network failures or underperformance, between the owner of the infrastructure and the service provider over the common infrastructure. There is still debate on these issues that could change the business models of MNOs and it is related to concepts like revenue and mechanisms for risk sharing.

2.1.2. End user of connectivity

Until now the connectivity is provided by using SIM cards (or recently eSIM in some higher end phones) and two business models dominate the sector.

In the first model, the connectivity is provided through the mobile phone of the users, utilizing an existing contract (post or prepaid) that the user has with an MNO (or MVNO). Users can use their devices or connect them to the vehicles (in the case of newer cards) to visualize the information and interact with the offered applications. Another option is that the vehicle has installed the necessary applications and connects to the network (through an installed SIM in the car).

There are two main platforms that dominate the market built around the Google and Apple ecosystem. Both these platforms have dedicated marketplaces where end users

may purchase applications that are uploaded by the application providers. For example, users who have vehicle with Android Automotive OS can install the applications directly onto their vehicle's infotainment system, while in the case of Android Auto users they can install the applications in their phone and connect to compatible vehicles in order to display a driver-optimized version of the application directly on the vehicles' display unit.

The main categories that the applications can be classified are the following:

- Messaging applications
- Media applications
- Navigation applications

The main difference between these two options regarding connectivity is that in the case that the OS is installed in the car there is a SIM card that is installed in the car and the connection to the mobile network is done through this. MNOs have already wholesale agreements with OEMs constructing vehicles providing them with connectivity. Then OEMs offer the opportunity to buyers of their vehicles to subscribe to premium packages in order to get access to the connectivity options that include navigation and streaming services. The cost of the connectivity is thus paid upfront by the vehicle owner to the OEM that has the wholesale agreement with the MNO. This is an evolution from the traditional B2B (or B2C) model to an evolved B2B2B (or B2B2C) model in which the buyer of the SIM card is different than the one that uses the connection.

These models are expected to further evolve in the future and especially in applications related to road safety as issues like accountability, ownership of data and regulation are constituting a complex environment with no discrete boundaries between the different roles. This changes the current business model of MNOs that will not interact directly with their end-users (as now) and thus are afraid that they will see their profit margins reduce.

Concluding, some of the different models regarding the customer of the connectivity are the following:

- The price is paid upfront and included within the price of the vehicle. The OEM has an agreement with the MNOs, acts as an intermediate and provides the compensation to the MNO (or MVNO). The end user has a contract with the OEM for the provision of services.
- A variation of the previous model is that the service is offered as an added value subscription service to end-users that are interested. The charging mechanism in

that case can be by monthly subscription and include also different metrics like the number of connected devices, the volume of data consumed, etc.

- The end-user pays directly to the MNO. The difference with the existing model is that the charging mechanism will use tiers for the different levels of QoS that is provided. In contrast to an OEM, an MNO does not provide the end-user application. The end-user is therefore responsible to ensure that contractual QoS with an MNO meets the requirements of the end-user used applications.

2.1.3. QoS charging

Currently MNOs offer connectivity programs with unlimited data included but on a best effort basis with no guaranteed QoS. Future 5G applications are expected to have strict requirements regarding aspects like latency or data rate that will require additional investments from MNOs. The main question is who will pay and how much for these new requirements. There are already arguments from the MNOs about getting a compensation from OTTs and a debate is open.

From the perspective of MNOs, 5G network slicing will offer them the opportunity to provide priority to services with better granularity than existing models.

When MNOs fully deploy their 5G SA networks, they will have the ability to create slices based on the user requirements, but it is not yet clear who they plan to get compensation for their network resources. Some options regarding the charging include models based on consumption and charging for premiums in cases that a certain level of QoS is required.

2.1.4. Cross-border connectivity

One more topic for debate is the provision of continuous and uninterrupted operation of the service while crossing borders of countries. Although there are existing agreements between operators, seamless roaming with strict requirements that 5G is promising is an ongoing challenge both from technical, business and regulatory sides. When moving from one operator to another, the QoS, especially for services in the automotive vertical (like remote driving or V2X communications), must be maintained. In the EU, the current regulation offers the same tariffs across EU for roamers as the ones they have in their home network. In the new 5G deployments it will be challenging for operators to share the resources among their own users and visitors especially in areas with limited resources. The impact of the different options strongly depends by the geographical

footprint of the operator and the ongoing commercial agreements that it has with operators in other countries. It is worth mentioning that this issue is something that EU operators will have to face in contrast to their counterparts in countries like USA and China where there are operators that provide national coverage.

2.2. Actors and roles

In order to understand the business model around the 5G-IANA platform, it is important to capture how value is created in a complex system with a lot of interdependencies. In this analysis we will use the value network to describe all the interrelations within the ecosystem.

The following definitions are used in the following sections:

- **Actor:** an entity that participates in the business model, and can provide or consume services.
- **Role:** the functionality of each actor that participates in the business model. An actor can take one or more of the roles, while a role can be undertaken by several actors.
- **Relationship:** the interaction between two roles in the model.

This section provides an overview of the different roles that have been identified in the 5G-IANA ecosystem, the analysis has been presented in D6.1 but is presented also here for the consistency of the deliverable. The different roles can be grouped in the following categories as illustrated in Figure 1.

- **Infrastructure providers:** that provide all types of infrastructure resources
- **Vendors:** that provide both HW and SW
- **Service creation and provisioning:** creators and providers of services
- **nApp related:** creation and provisioning of nApps
- **End Users:** that are the ultimate consumers of the developed services.

Figure 1: Roles within the 5G-IANA ecosystem

In more details, the following roles are part of the 5G-IANA ecosystem:

- **MNOs:** they deploy and operate the telecommunication infrastructure that is required for connectivity (core and Radio Access Network - RAN). They own the physical equipment such as base stations, antennas, switches, etc.
- **Cloud Infrastructure Providers:** they provide all required storage, cloud computing and corresponding networking resources (CPUs, RAM, storage). These can be in a central (cloud location) or in a local location (in edge servers).
- **Road Infrastructure operators:** they are responsible for the deployment, operation, and maintenance of the road infrastructure. They can also own and operate road-side facilities such as ICT equipment, cameras and sensors located in the road networks.
- **HW Vendors:** they provide all type of hardware to all interested parties, for example base stations, antennas, switches, routers, servers, network cards, sensors, cameras, CPUs, RAM, Road-Side Units (RSU), On-Board Units (OBU), entertainment systems, etc.
- **SW vendors:** they provide all the necessary generic software that is required by all other parties. For example, the firmware that is required for the hardware devices, all type of software for the entertainment systems, etc. This role does not include

the development and provision of nApps and Application and Network Functions (AFs/NFs).

- **OEMs:** entities that are in charge of manufacturing all type of vehicles.
- **Service Creators:** all type of service creation entities such as SMEs, and software developers.
- **Service Providers:** they are responsible for providing the service to end users (for example Intelligent Driving, HD maps, etc.).
- **nApp Developers and Application and Network Functions Developers:** they develop the Application Functions (AFs) and Network Functions (NFs) that can be used as building blocks for creating nApps, they are also responsible for the development of nApps.
- **nApp Providers and Application and Network Functions Providers:** they are responsible for providing the AFs and NFs to be on-boarded through the functionalities provided by the nApp Toolkit platform component, they are also the ones that provide the nApps either to end users or service creators/providers.
- **End Users:** includes all type of users that are the recipients of the services. They can be individual users (B2C or B2B2C) or business end-users (B2B or B2B2B). Some examples are vehicle owners, drivers, passengers or pedestrians for end users and transport operators, traffic management, freight and logistics, or providers of public services as business users.

Evidently, a certain stakeholder in the emerging ecosystem may well hold more than one of these roles as will be described in the following scenarios.

2.2.1. Discrete roles adopted by actors

This is the simplest scenario in which each actor adopts only one role. The value network for this case is presented in Figure 2 that was introduced in D6.1.

Figure 2: 5G-IANA reference model

Regarding the relations in the reference model, the arrows indicate the relation among the different roles, while the direction of the arrow represents the direction of the service flow. The flow of the revenue is in the opposite direction of the arrow, although in some cases there is revenue sharing agreement (in that case there are bidirectional flows and arrows). We have to note that there are also other relationships between the roles (for example HW vendors provide equipment to all other members of the ecosystem) but these relationships are not examined since they are not affecting the business model of the AOEP.

The business relationships in the reference model are the following:

- **HW equipment:** it represents the relationship between actors for the provisioning of ICT related equipment. It is provided by the HW vendor to the infrastructure providers and the 5G-IANA platform.
- **SW:** it represents the provision of SW by the SW provider to the HW vendor, the infrastructure providers and the 5G-IANA platform.

- **ICT Resources:** it is a general term that includes all kind of resources (connectivity, computational resources, RSU, etc) that are provided by the infrastructure providers. This is a relation among the MNO, the Cloud Infrastructure Provider and the Road Infrastructure provider and the 5G-IANA platform.
- **Resources (vehicles):** it includes the vehicles that are provided by the vehicle manufacturer to the 5G-IANA platform.
- **nApps:** these are the nApps developed by the nApp developers and are tested in the 5G-IANA platform.
- **5G Services:** it represents the provision of 5G services that are ready to be consumed by the end users. These are provided by the service creator to the service provider that is the one that interacts with end users. It can also be provided by the service creator to the 5G-IANA platform in case that it is a service that can be used by other services.
- **AOEP Services:** it describes the portfolio of services that are provided by the 5G-IANA platform, it includes the use of the platform for experimentation, consulting and training services.

2.2.2. MNO acts as experimentation and service integrator

In this scenario, the MNO has an aggregated strategy and takes the roles of MNO, Cloud Infrastructure provider, owns the 5G-IANA experimentation platform while at the same time creates and provides the services to end users. An MNO can adopt this aggressive strategy either because it identifies a gap in the service creation and provisioning that has as a result the investments that made are underutilised and no extra revenues are coming. Another reason for this aggressive strategy is that it foresees that new players want to enter the market and get part of the revenues similar to the current case in which OTT players are providing services using the network infrastructure developed by network operators without sharing any of the revenues they get or contribute to the cost of network deployment. They own the necessary for experimentation 5G network resources, so it is easier and natural for them to take the role of hosting the 5G-IANA AOEP; they would require resources from the Vehicle manufacturers but they already have a relationship for providing connectivity to their vehicles so it will be easier to expand this relationship. On the other hand, OEMs as seen from the past are reluctant to take additional roles, so this is a model that they might prefer. MNOs need also to establish a connection with the nApps providers and developers; owning the 5G-IANA platform that can be used for testing and validation can give MNOs an advantage in order

to establish this connection. The actors and the roles that they take and their relationships are illustrated in Figure 3.

The main drawback for the MNO is that they must develop services for verticals that is something new to them and might lack the skills or the experience and knowledge to understand the specific needs of the vertical users.

Figure 3: MNO as experimentation and service integrator

2.2.3. MNO acts as experimentation integrator and service provider

This is a variation of the previous scenario in which the MNOs realise that service creation for verticals might be too risky, so they are not adopting the role of the service creator and leave room for existing and new players to take this role. SMEs and third parties that have experience in service development in the vertical might be appropriate candidates for this role. They do not want to be familiar with the nApp development and provision, a role that again SMEs and startups with experience in 5G networks can undertake. The value network for this scenario is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: MNO only as experimentation integrator and service provider

This scenario allows more new entrants to enter the ecosystem, while at the same time it provides some advantages to the MNOs as they are not expanding into roles that they are not familiar with. Regarding the role of the experimentation platform (like 5G-IANA), this is a scenario that is already adopted by the main operators in the form of Open Labs that they are creating in collaboration with vendors and/or research centers and academia. The main drawback for the whole ecosystem is that they can control and decide who will have access to the platform while they can also enforce their own pricing policies to service creators.

2.2.4. MNO acts as experimentation integrator only

In this case, the MNO takes only one additional role, that of the owner of the experimentation platform, leaving more space for innovation and new entrants to participate in the ecosystem (Figure 5). From the ecosystem's view of point this seems to be the most attractive compared to the other options.

Figure 5: MNO as experimentation integrator

2.2.5. Cooperation among actors for experimentation

A variation of the previous scenario is the co-ownership of the experimentation platform among different actors such as infrastructure providers, service creators, and OEMs. Each of these actors can contribute with their resources and expertise to this common effort, similar to the case that partners of 5G-IANA cooperate for increasing their benefits. This variation is presented in Figure 6.

There are different options on how this cooperative model can be implemented: it could be a new legal entity in which the different actors participate with shares or contribution in kind, or there could be a Public Private Partnership (PPP) in which the public sector also participates to increase the social benefits.

Figure 6: Cooperation model

2.2.1. Experimentation platform as an MVNO

A different scenario is that in which the 5G-IANA platform also takes the role of MNO by becoming a MVNO. This implies that an agreement must be made among the MNO and the 5G-IANA platform regarding the network resources similar to the ones that MVNOs have. It will provide more freedom, depending on the type of MVNO, to the experimentation platform than the models where MNO provides the resources. Until now, there are no 5G MVNOs in the market to the best of our knowledge, as there are several issues regarding charging principles among the two parties that must be solved. The value network is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Experimentation as MVNO

To conclude, the different models that will be adopted depend mainly on the strategy that the MNO will follow since in most of the countries the MNO is the owner of the spectrum making their participation in all scenarios mandatory. The allocation of spectrum for the creation of private networks or the creation of MVNOs is something that can change these conditions and create new models in the future.

2.3. Future service provisioning scenarios

For SMEs that aim to successfully develop applications for the automotive sector, and therefore to ensure an economical success of 5G-IANA, at least one testbed environment which provides following capabilities and features is recommendable:

- 5G-IANA platform(s) with high capabilities to allow the development, inauguration, and monitoring of a wide range of automotive applications.
- OBUs and RSUs, on which applications can be hosted, and to which sensors required for an application can be connected to.

- A 5G-IANA testing area with tracks on which the application can be tested with vehicles.
- LTE/5G coverage of the 5G-IANA testing area, ideally with the flexibility to configure the mobile network for 5G NSA operation as well as 5G SA operation with different network slicing types. For testing of low latency applications, also MEC-Server capability should be available.

Different ecosystem owners for automotive applications can be identified, for which automotive applications can be developed. Testing in a 5G-IANA testbed should be flexible enough to allow application development and testing which reflects how a developed application is deployed within an ecosystem. The assumption is that the value network that is adopted is the one that all actors have discrete roles (Figure 2). The following scenarios provide some examples from the view of a service provider in the automotive vertical.

The first one is a simple evolution of today's business model; applications are provided through the marketplace and can be installed on the mobile phones of the users. These types of applications will be based on a best effort connection and thus no strict QoS is expected to be required. The 5G-IANA platform can be used to develop the application while an existing subscription with an MNO will be used.

The second scenario is the case of an OEM that has an agreement with MNOs to get a number of slices with different QoS requirement in each of them. These slices can be used for the provision of different types of services depending on the need of each of the applications. The service developer can use the 5G-IANA platform to create and test the application using the available resources and configuring the necessary slice based on the application requirements. To offer the service, it must make an agreement with the OEM to configure the appropriate slice and use it to offer the service to end users.

The third scenario is related to the provision of services in a private network that are starting to be created in a number of countries within industrial premises, harbors etc. The owners of the private network want to provide services within that network. In that case the development of the service can be done in the 5G-IANA platform either using the resources of the platform or another option will be to have an agreement to use the 5G-IANA platform but with the resources that the private network has available.

In all scenarios that are presented the focus is on service delivery so only the involved actors are highlighted in the value networks that are presented.

2.3.1. Ecosystem around an Application Store

A service creator (for example an SME) uses the 5G-IANA platform to develop an application which can be installed and used on smartphones and/or on servers hosted in the cloud. Examples of applications like these may include applications that provide route information with a map, reservation of a parking spot, or automatic payment of an inner-city toll when the vehicle enters an inner-city checkpoint. All the aforementioned examples have no high bandwidth or latency requirements, so no dedicated slice is required.

The application developer can offer the application via the ecosystem of an App-Store, such as the Google or Apple Store.

A smartphone owner can download the application from the App-Store. The smartphone owner has a contract with a mobile operator, which specifies the QoS for mobile connectivity, such as the maximum throughput rate available for the smartphone owner, or the maximum data volume available per month. It is up to the smartphone owner to check if the application requirements with respect to throughput rates, data volume demand, latency, etc. is met complying to the subscription.

Figure 8: Application store ecosystem

The value network for the service provisioning for this scenario is presented in Figure 9. The development of services in that scenario can be done through the 5G-IANA platform, while the end user will be the party responsible for the connectivity. The 5G-IANA

platform can additionally be used as an alternative marketplace for these types of applications, although in most of the cases it will be difficult to enter this market since the current established actors (Apple or Google) will dominate the market.

Figure 9: Service available in Application Store

2.3.2. Vehicular Manufacturer

Vehicular manufacturers execute strict control on the OBUs built into their vehicles. They often also make contracts with national mobile network operators to connect the OBUs with the manufacturer’s cloud and/or MEC Server infrastructure.

As example, the (fictive) vehicular manufacturer Aquila has made contracts with multiple mobile operators for three 5G network slices (see also Figure 10):

- a) The V2X slice 1 is used for vehicles which support autonomous driving. As autonomous driving is latency critical, the car manufacturer has agreed with mobile operators that they provide MEC-Server infrastructure to allow data processing close to the vehicles. Aquila and mobile network operators also agreed that band 28 (700MHz/10MHz + 10MHz, FDD), which provides very good coverage, is used for autonomous data transmission. They also agreed that a quota of 10% of band 28 is always available for the service, i.e. even under high cell load

situations, Aquila will get 10% of the operator’s band 28 radio resources, i.e. at least 1MHz. A network slice meeting Aquila’s requirement for autonomous driving is in our example (see figure) only available in three countries. Therefore, Aquila cannot provide these services in other countries where its vehicles are in use.

- b) The V2X slice 2 is used for remote driving.
- c) The eMBB slice is used for a range of non-time critical applications, such as vehicle diagnostics and infotainment.

Figure 10: Vehicular manufacturer ecosystem

To develop an application for a vehicle manufacturer ecosystem, not only the 5G-IANA platform to develop the application is required, but also an environment to test the application. If the application targets autonomous driving, a network slice should be configured in the 5G-IANA test field which mimics the car manufacturer’s network slice for autonomous slicing. For instance, if band 28 is not available in the testbed, the network slice can be configured on a different band with similar connectivity properties. If the application developer gets a subscription via the car manufacturer, then application testing can be directly done on the car manufacturer’s network slice. In this case, the 5G-IANA platform is sufficient for application development. The application can be offered within the countries that the OEM has agreements to the MNOs (that can differ from slice to slice).

The value network for this service provisioning scenario is presented in Figure 11. As shown, there exists a new relation between the OEMs and Infrastructure providers. OEMs purchase ICT resources from cloud providers and slices from the MNO. The end user interacts with the OEM to get the service without having to deal with connectivity issues since these are taken care from the OEM.

Figure 11: Vehicle manufacturer scenario

There are already solutions presented in the market, in which vehicles are equipped with two embedded SIMs (eSIM), with the one used for vehicle services such as eCall, navigation or traffic information and the second for the driver's private information and in-vehicle entertainment services [3]. We expect this type of service provisioning to be adopted in the future from OEMs.

2.3.3. Private Network

At major logistic sites such as harbors, open-pit mining, or large production sites such as in the petro-chemical industry, the site owners often operate a private mobile network. The private mobile network may be either provided as virtual network by a commercial mobile network operator or built by a site owner using a private license. For instance, in

Band n78 in Germany, the frequency range from 3700 to 3800MHz is reserved for private networks.

As in the case of the Vehicular Manufacturer Ecosystem, a private network owner can specify several network slices for the vehicles operating on its site. And as in the Vehicular Manufacturer Ecosystem, an application developer can use the 5G-IANA platform to develop a new application and use either a 5G-IANA testbed or the private network owner infrastructure for testing.

Figure 12: Private network ecosystem

The value network for the provisioning of the service is presented in Figure 13. In this case the end users are limited within the area of the private network. The service provider interacts with the owner of the private network (that can be either the facility owner or the MNO that owns the network) in order to create the necessary slices that are required for the different types of services. These are provided to the service provider that is responsible for the delivery of services to end users.

The number of private networks is increasing mainly because end users understand the potential of the private networks and also MNOs are trying to expand the sources of their revenues. In the future we expect that the number of private networks will increase making business models also valid for adoption. The owner of the network depends on the regulation in the different countries; if local licenses are allowed (as in Germany) other actors except MNOs can also enter the market for deploying and running the network.

Especially in the USA infrastructure providers such as Amazon offer the opportunity to create and operate private networks for their clients. But not in all the cases they compete with MNOs; there are also cooperative scenarios in which MNOs provide the spectrum and connectivity while cloud providers the ICT resources.

Figure 13: Private network scenario

3. BUSINESS MODELS FOR 5G-IANA AOEP

The first version of the envisioned business model for the 5G-IANA AOEP was introduced in *D6.1: Market Analysis and Initial Business Model* [1]. This chapter provides an updated version with more details on the cost and revenue models. The proposal presented here and different options regarding the future of the 5G-IANA platform are the outcome of the discussions among the partners of the consortium. We expect to fine tune and modify if needed our approach during the validation phases of the Open Call, using as input the feedback of third parties that will use the platform in order to better understand their expectations and needs. The outcome of this process will be reported in *D6.4: Techno-economic analysis and sustainability of 5G-IANA business models*.

3.1. Unique Value Proposition

The main value proposition is the 5G-IANA experimental platform, that is formed by a number of elements. The most important elements are the resources (physical and virtualized), the AF/NF repository, the nApp toolkit, the network management and orchestration module, the distributed AI/ML framework.

The nApp toolkit will facilitate the on-boarding of new nApps in the 5G-IANA platform and will leverage the composition of new services by using the available building blocks.

The modular design that is used in the overall architecture of the 5G-IANA platform enables the separation of the roles between service developers and service providers.

The flexibility and openness of the virtualized infrastructure can make easier for new entrants to design, create and test their own applications and services.

3.2. Services offered by the 5G-IANA AOEP

The main service that the 5G-IANA platform will offer will be the actual experimentation, while along with this a number of added value services can be provided to interested parties. The following sections provide more details for each of these services.

3.2.1. Experimentation services

Experimenting in the 5G-IANA platform will be the main service provided to external third-party developers that want to develop new 5G services targeted to the Automotive vertical (or any other vertical) as some of the nApps can be considered as vertical

agnostic and reused to compose new nApps for other verticals. The experimentation includes a set of aspects such as onboarding their own nApps, using nApps offered in the platform, utilizing the nApp “Starter-kit”, validating their services and using the monitoring and analytics capabilities. All these aspects can be used partially or as a whole by the interested third parties based on their needs and existing knowledge and development requirements.

3.2.2. Support services

These are support services at high level that can facilitate the experimentation in the 5G-IANA platform. It can include topics such as how third parties can use the platform and available resources. The form of the support can be by providing supporting material in the form of multimedia such as videos providing guidance to the different aspects of the experimentation process based on the received feedback during the onboarding of third parties. Also, a wiki with answers to most common questions can be created. Examples from the UCs developed within 5G-IANA and the services that will be created during the Open Call can provide valuable information. This type of services will be targeted to experienced users that are familiar with 5G networks and application development and will only provide details on how they can use the platform for experimentation. In case that support is required with a guaranteed response time, a Service Level Agreement (SLA) can be signed defining the details.

3.2.3. Training services

One of the main activities foreseen for the 5G-IANA platform is the provision of training services to third parties that want to take advantage of all the provided functionalities. This is an extension of the services included in the training and will provide support for third parties on how they can onboard their nApps and create a service using the available tools or can also be extended to include assistance during the experimentation and validation phases. The training will be provided by direct assistance and interaction via video or phone conference platforms. Through these interactive sessions third parties can receive answers to more complex topics that are not covered by the support services. The training services will be targeted to more experienced users that are already familiar with the development and creation of services and want the personalised training for resolving any issues they will face.

3.2.4. Consulting services

Consulting services will be provided to users with less experience in the development of 5G services. It can include topics like the creation of nApps and services (using existing nApps), technical assistance on improving their services, and assistance in the validation of their idea (both technical and business wise). The main difference compared to the training service will be that the consulting one will cover more broad topics and not just be about the operation of the platform. The topics will be tailored to the specific needs of each customer. Also, the service will be in a form of a live interaction with the people of the 5G-IANA platform who will undertake these tasks. Not only technical but also business mentoring is foreseen to be provided. Technical validation can assist them in the improvement of their service (for example consume less resources, optimization of the performance, etc.), while business validation will provide consultancy in the assessment of the market opportunities and the creation of an initial business plan.

3.2.5. Using nApps developed by third-parties

This is an optional service that might be provided in case that there are third-parties that want to offer their services through the platform to service providers or other developers. It is similar to a marketplace where developers will deposit their nApps along with the appropriate documentation on how these can be used. This functionality is not foreseen as part of the work implemented in the duration of the project but is something that can be considered as an additional offering that needs to be developed after the end of the project. If implemented, it can provide additional source of revenues using a revenue sharing agreement between the service developer and the platform based on a rule like the reuse of the components from other parties. Another option will be to provide their components and get a discount on the other services.

3.3. Main cost drivers/categories

The costs that are foreseen are associated with the provisioning of the services and driven by the key activities of the 5G-IANA platform. In this deliverable only a description of the different categories of the foreseen costs is included, as the values that will be used for the creation of the final business plan will be presented in D6.4 that will be delivered at the end of the project.

3.3.1. Costs for the maintenance and operation of the platform

It includes the salaries of the people that will be responsible for maintaining the operation of the 5G-IANA platform. They will be responsible to sustain the final version of the platform that will be delivered after the end of the project securing that the platform will remain operational. The main tasks will be associated with the maintenance of the testbeds, the different HW components and keeping all the software modules updated. Telecom and software engineers or DevOps are expected to undertake this role. We have to comment here that we expect the salaries will differ based on the profile and expertise of the employee and also the country of residence.

It also includes the cost for all licences associated with the operation of the platform and the infrastructure that will be required.

3.3.2. Costs for further developing the platform

It includes both OPEX and CAPEX associated with the addition of new functionalities in the platform, which for example can be the development of new nApps, provisioning of new resources, etc. OPEX includes the associated costs for the development of the new functionalities such as personnel costs, licences required and IT resources for hosting the VMs (at this stage the IaaS model is considered to be more cost effective). CAPEX is associated with the expansion of the testbeds (or the inclusion of new ones), the HW used for experimentation such as OBUs, RSUs, cars (for the automotive vertical) or the extension of the network coverage and new network equipment (end user devices).

These costs are strongly associated with the type of services that will be provided by the platform. For example, one option will be to continue to target only end-users in the Automotive Vertical, while the option to provide services to other verticals will also be considered as there are functional elements of the platform that are vertical agnostic.

3.3.3. Costs for maintaining the portal/website

These include the costs for maintaining the website with all required information updated such as the support material. It is estimated that at least one web developer can undertake these duties. Another option will be to outsource this activity to a web developing company that will redesign the site giving a more commercial approach and also link it with the marketing and promotional activities that must be undertaken to increase the end-users of the platform.

3.3.4. Costs related to training services

For the provision of the training services, a pool of experts that are familiar with the operation of the platform will be required. They will be responsible for creating the necessary training material and also responding to inquiries made by users.

3.3.5. Costs related to consulting services

This will probably be one of the most demanding services as it will need personnel that are familiar with the platform and can assist both from technical and business perspective. A pool of experts like software and telecommunication engineers along with business consultants are expected to be the main candidates for providing these consulting services.

3.3.6. Marketing costs

This includes the costs associated with the promotion of the 5G-IANA platform to interested parties. At first, the marketing plan must be defined based on the final business plan that will be delivered at the end of the project, using that as a first input while after discussions the marketing plan will be drafted including the customer segments that must be reached (Automotive only or other verticals), how these can be reached, and a roadmap of all activities that must be undertaken. This can be done by marketing experts that will become personnel of the entity that will be responsible for the operation of the platform or provided as an outsourcing service (at least for the first years of the operation).

3.4. Revenues/pricing models

To ensure the financial viability of the platform, a source of incoming revenues must be defined. Revenues can come from different sources such as public entities in form of grants, inventors and users of the platform, or a combination of these sources. This report provides details on the revenues from third parties, it examines the service offerings that can be provided and the different pricing models that can be adopted.

3.4.1. Experimentation (AOEP)

Different pricing models can be examined for the main service provided to external third-party developers. The main driver for the calculation of revenues can be the usage of resources and more specifically the time that the platform will be booked for

experimentation. Since all resources and especially the radio resources are scarce and not easily accessible from developers, this is something that must be considered when determining the actual pricing. The consumption of resources of the 5G network is something that developers should monitor since it is something that will incur additional costs in the provisioning of the service.

3.4.2. Support

No additional revenue from the basic support service is expected to be included into the basic fees for experimentation since no additional effort will be required. Only in cases where support must be provided based on specific KPIs (for example within 24 hours), a charge will be applied according to the terms of the SLA signed.

3.4.3. Training / Consulting

For the training and consulting services the revenue calculation is usually based on an hourly or daily rate according to the consumed resources. There can be a flat rate in case limited usage is needed (just a couple of hours per month) or some reductions in case that more frequent engagement is needed. The price can also change based on the required response time.

3.4.4. Service bundles

Different bundles can be created including components of the different type of services that the 5G-IANA platform will offer. At this stage only the plan that includes the tier of the bundles and the types of services that these will include has been developed, whereas information about the pricing will be developed in D6.4 where the costs will be quantified, and the financial sustainability of the platform will be evaluated.

The initial plan that includes the different types of bundles is presented in Table 1. The basic service (it might be provided for free) will include limited access to the platform (and resources) with no guarantee that these will be available when the user wants, with no other type of service included. It will be targeted to users that want to check the platform and examine if they are willing to purchase some of the offered services.

The other four other tiers of services: bronze, silver, gold and platinum provide more value-added services with different combinations trying to cover all possible requests. These will be reviewed and modified if needed, based on the input received from the Open Call and the feedback from external users.

Table 1: Foreseen service bundles

Bundle	Experimentation	Support	Training	Consulting	Customer segment
Basic	Limited time and no guaranteed slots	Existing material	-	-	Novice users, users that want to check the platform
Bronze	On the go (low priority)	Existing material	Fixed Price	Fixed Price	Service developers with limited requirements
Silver	Includes experimentation time (higher priority than bronze)	Existing material + SLA support	Includes a number of days	Fixed Price	Service developers (low number of services) that require training
Gold	Includes experimentation time (higher limit and priority than silver)	Existing material + SLA support	Fixed Price	Includes a number of days	Service developers (low number of services) that value consulting more than training
Platinum	Includes experimentation time (higher priority access to resources)	Existing material + SLA support	Includes a number of days	Includes a number of days	Service developers that develop a number of services (increased needs)

4. BUSINESS MODELS FOR 5G-IANA USE CASES

This section presents more details about the business models associated with each of the UCs. Information regarding the targeted market, the involved stakeholders, the business impact, foreseen costs, and revenue sources is presented along with the Lean Canvas that has been developed. The Lean Canvas is a business modelling tool - a variation of the Business Model Canvas tailored for startups.

4.1. UC1: Remote driving

This use case is about the integration and validation of advanced remote driving functionalities in the open and enhanced experimentation 5G-IANA platform. A vehicle connected through 5G is controlled remotely via a teleoperation platform. It sends information based on its on-board sensors and video cameras. The 5G enabled vehicle is equipped with an OBU. At the edge, an AI/ML algorithm is processed and added on top of the video, providing information about the different elements located while driving on the road, such as pedestrians, cars, or traffic signals. An additional warning feature is included to provide the driver additional information and/or stopping when a potential accident is about to happen.

4.1.1. Targeted market

The main vertical stakeholders potentially interested in the services offered by this use case are industrial companies with automated guided vehicles that need remote driving services in factories, industrial parks or similar venues, and automotive OEMs.

4.1.2. Market assessment

The use of remote driving, although with different features, has been demonstrated in several EU projects such as 5G-Blueprint, 5G-MOBIX, 5GCroCo or iNGENIOUS. Several companies in the market also provide similar solutions, although they usually are proprietary with limited open access.

4.1.3. Stakeholders involved

The main internal stakeholders involved in this use case are the following:

- 5COMM (nApp developer and vehicle provider)
- NOKIA (network provider)
- UBI and NXW (IANA platform)

- VICOM (tracking algorithm nApp provider).

There are also several external stakeholders that may benefit from the use case:

Table 2: Involved stakeholders in UC1

Stakeholder	Role	Expected benefit
Automotive companies	Integrate UC1 feature in their offering	Automotive companies will increase their offering by providing remote driving services in their vehicles.
Public Authorities	Use the developed features in “smart-city” projects	Decrease risk of road accident and more accurate traffic management in critical areas.
Industrial companies	Integrate UC1 features in their automated guided vehicles	Industrial companies could implement the remote driving services in some of their AGVs for controlling them remotely when needed.

4.1.4. Business Impact

UC1 can provide greater comfort to people when performing certain types of activities that do not require human presence. This nApp can cause a great impact on the transport industry, since it can be adapted to large vehicles to transport material to sites in dangerous areas, transport dangerous substances, transport goods to places that are far away. Automotive industries enabling such a nApp would safeguard the safety of the driver, thus saving resources, and in the case of long journeys they would not need to stop the vehicle for the driver to rest.

4.1.5. Main costs

CAPEX related costs are the deployment of an OBU on the vehicles that use the nApp or a particular fleet of vehicles if the service needs to be expanded. OPEX related costs include software development tasks and training of future drivers of the vehicles. Some other important costs associated are 5G infrastructure costs, marketing and promotion, maintenance, and upgrades, as well as legal and regulatory compliance arrangements.

4.1.6. Expected source of revenues

Based on the prototype developed, revenues are expected on three main axes, namely the provision of the technological solution from the sale of patents to OEMs, the production as tier1 of the specific communication units or the provision of the service in collaboration with OEMs.

4.1.7. Lean Canvas

The lean canvas for UC1 is presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Lean Canvas for UC1

4.2. UC2: Manoeuvre coordination for autonomous driving

The use case aims to showcase a manoeuvre coordination service, available thanks to the 5G-IANA infrastructure, capable of lowering the risk of collision in complex junction scenarios by describing suitable paths and priorities for connected, eventually automated, vehicles directed by a shared coordination system. It facilitates AVs and human driven cars interaction at gatherings, complex intersections, and clogged traffic. The use case will include autonomous and traditional cars together with Virtual Vehicles that can be put in at will to recreate realistic traffic conditions. Virtual simulated vehicles, fully integrated into the AOEP, will also serve as a powerful tool to facilitate experimentation throughout the 5G-IANA platform ecosystem.

4.2.1. Targeted market

Industrial companies with automated guided vehicles, automotive OEMs.

4.2.2. Market assessment

The possibility to integrate the 5G networks into Autonomous driving solutions, implies the change to integrate the results in different markets and real contexts. In this sense, the UC2 will focus also in non-automotive sector to maximize the project results.

4.2.3. Stakeholders involved

We can consider internal Stakeholders the project partners involved in the UC development:

- NOKIA (Testbed and 5G Network provider)
- 5COMM (Develops on-vehicle integration software and develops VNFs)
- LINKS (OBU provider with 5G connectivity)
- NXW (Orchestration and load balancing)
- UBITECH (Orchestration).

In the table below we can take in to account external Stakeholders by categories:

Table 3: Involved stakeholders in UC2

Stakeholder	Role	Expected benefit
Insurance Providers	Integration of the features in associated telematics products, and decrease of insurance costs (by decreasing risks involved)	New insurance contracts where the driver liability can be shared with OEM's with at reduce annual cost rate.
Public Authorities	Use the developed features in "smart-city" projects	Decrease risk of road accident and more accurate traffic management in critical areas.
Public Transportation Authorities	City transportation management	More efficient public transportation system thanks to additional information and interaction with different actors involved.
Leasing, rental and Automotive companies	Integrate UC2 feature in telematics offerings.	Leasing, rental and Automotive companies will decrease the risk of road accidents for their fleets and, more in general, the community benefits from CO2 reduction and public health costs.

4.2.4. Business Impact

UC2 can provide a valid outcome for all the partners involved, because the expected results could be integrated not only in a vehicle but also in other types of system part of a smart city network. The nApps developed and used in the UC2 will be soon available on the market and in this case, we will be able to obtain a technological and business advantages.

4.2.5. Main costs

The main cost item will be related to the software developer tasks and for the neural learning training. In addition, we must take in consideration HW costs in the current shortage context.

4.2.6. Expected source of revenues

Starting from the results, the revenues can be obtained for the sub-systems development. Could be possible use part of the project outcomes in prototypes and/or new autonomous driving solutions.

4.2.7. Lean Canvas

The lean canvas that has been created for UC2 is presented in Figure 15.

The Lean Canvas		UC 2: Manoeuvre Coordination for Autonomous Driving		01-06-2023
				Iteration #1
<p>Problem</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intersection traversal for autonomous vehicles Intersection traversal safety Slow traffic flow at intersections <p>Alternative Solutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intersection traversal for AVs: AVs attempt to traverse intersections with incomplete information (vehicle sensing and map), leading to diffident and possibly unsafe manoeuvres Some intersections have dynamic traffic lights (which may depend on time of day or traffic conditions) aimed at improving flow and safety 	<p>Solution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimization of intersection traversal routes in terms of time and safety Best possible traffic flow reduces energy consumption and therefore pollution Lower computational burden on AVs regarding route planning Possibility to test on virtual environments <p>Key Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average traversal time Number of accidents/near misses Service and network level KPIs (service availability, service reliability, E2E latency) 	<p>Unique Value Proposition</p> <p>Our MCAD service will demonstrate the real potential of autonomous and connected vehicles, as it will globally optimize intersection traversal routes with the information and control available to it through the 5G-IANA platform. This global optimization is impossible for unconnected vehicles.</p>	<p>Unfair Advantage</p> <p>We possess the capability to develop, test and deploy this solution on virtual, real and augmented reality environments. Other attempts usually end in simulated environments due to the lack of vehicles or connectivity infrastructure.</p> <p>Channels</p> <p>5G-IANA communication and dissemination efforts.</p>	<p>Customer Segments</p> <p>All road users experience the inefficiencies and stress of intersections, with transport authorities always attempting to mitigate these issues.</p> <p>Early adopters</p> <p>AV manufacturers and road maintainers (transport authorities).</p>
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SW development AV preparation HW needed to run the SW (available from 5G-IANA) Testing: Booking private areas for initial testing (available from 5G-IANA) Testing: Permits to deploy on public roads (future) 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <p>Services: Application of MCAD in road networks.</p>		
PRODUCT		MARKET		

Figure 15: Lean Canvas for UC2

4.3. UC3: Virtual Bus tour

The virtual bus tour is an application that harnesses the power of 5G technology and Virtual Reality (VR) to provide users with an immersive and seamless experience of

attending a live bus tour from any remote location. Leveraging a 5G network infrastructure, the tour utilizes an onboard 360-degree camera to stream high-quality video directly to the user’s VR headset. To ensure the utmost immersion and attractiveness of the service, high-quality avatars have been incorporated into the virtual bus tour. These avatars provide users with a sense of presence and enable them to interact with the virtual environment, enhancing the overall experience.

4.3.1. Targeted market

The preliminary analysis targeted cities, municipalities, touristic agencies, cultural institutions, and educational establishments. The final target market will be reported in D6.4.

4.3.2. Market assessment

Several established players in the virtual tour market already offer solutions across various industries. These companies have built a presence and customer base, examples include well-known virtual tour providers like Matterport and YouVisit. Other competitors come from the VR industry, companies specializing in VR content creation and 360° video production. They may offer similar immersive experiences but may not focus specifically on bus tours. These providers include EON Reality, Oculus Studios, and Google Expeditions. A detailed analysis of the competitive landscape will be reported in D6.4.

4.3.3. Stakeholders involved

The main internal stakeholders involved in this use case are the following:

- NOKIA (Provider of Testbed/5G Network)
- UBI-NXW (Orchestration platform provider)
- LINKS (Provider of OBU with 5G connectivity)

The indicative stakeholders for UC3 are presented in Table 4. A more detailed stakeholder analysis will be reported in D6.4.

Table 4: Involved Stakeholders in UC3

Stakeholder	Role	Expected benefit
Users	Remote attendees of the virtual bus tour	Experience live bus tours remotely, explore new destinations, access immersive and interactive content, convenience of attending tours from

Stakeholder	Role	Expected benefit
		anywhere and cost savings compared to physical travel.
5G Network Providers	Provide the underlying 5G network infrastructure	Provide a new service to the infotainment vertical sector. At the same time, showcase the capabilities of the 5G network and potential revenue stream generation from 5G technology adoption, through specialized offerings for virtual tour participants.
Tourism Agencies	Promote and sell virtual bus tour packages	Offer a unique and innovative tourism experience to their end-users, broaden their product offerings, increase customer satisfaction and engagement and differentiate themselves from competitors.
Education Institutions	Integrate virtual bus tours into their curriculum or educational programs	Enhance learning experiences for students, access to immersive educational content, opportunity to offer virtual field trips, cost savings compared to physical excursions and potential for customized educational tours.
Local Councils and Municipalities	Support and promote virtual bus tours as part of their tourism and cultural initiatives	Showcase local attractions and heritage sites, attract virtual tourists, boost local economy, support tourism recovery efforts, strengthen cultural identity and community engagement.
Disabled Persons' Organizations	Advocate for accessibility and inclusion in virtual tour experiences	Improved accessibility for individuals with disabilities, enhanced participation and engagement and raise awareness about the needs of disabled individuals.

4.3.4. Business Impact

The virtual bus tour service has the potential to generate significant business impact through revenue generation, market expansion, strategic partnerships and contribution to economic development. The virtual bus tour service can create new revenue streams for HYP. By marketing the service to tourism boards, travel agencies, hotels, educational institutions, and corporate clients, HYP can generate revenue through service subscriptions, partnerships, and licensing agreements. The virtual bus tour service opens opportunities for market expansion, broadening HYP's customer base, by targeting diverse customer segments, including tourists, educational institutions, cultural organizations, and corporate clients. Collaboration with VR technology providers can also strengthen HYP's position by ensuring access to cutting-edge VR equipment and innovations. Lastly, by promoting cultural heritage, attracting tourists, and showcasing local landmarks, the virtual bus tour can drive tourism revenue and boost local

economies. More detailed business impact for UC3 will be revealed as the project progresses and will be reported in D6.4.

4.3.5. Main costs

Development and Infrastructure Costs, Marketing and Promotion Expenses, Personnel and Operational Costs, Partnership and Collaboration Costs, Maintenance and Upgrades, Legal and Regulatory Compliance. A more detailed view of the cost analysis for UC3 will be reported in D6.4, as the cost structure is expected to be clearer by then.

4.3.6. Expected source of revenues

Indicatively HYP will explore possibilities for revenue generation from subscription fees and ticket sales, corporate partnerships and private event bookings, content licensing and in-app purchases of additional content or features and/or merchandise sales (e.g., souvenirs delivered to the users' real-life location). The results from this analysis of different revenue models will be reported in D6.4.

4.3.7. Lean Canvas

The Lean Canvas		UC3: Virtual Bus Tour			31-05-2023	
					Iteration #1	
<p>Problem</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited accessibility and distance constraints for traditional bus tours - Inefficient network and computational resource consumption for streaming 360° video content - Lack of real-time interactivity and responsiveness in virtual tours <p>Alternative Solutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pre-recorded 360° video tours of various locations - Adaptive streaming techniques to adjust video quality based on the viewer's network conditions - Interactive elements to enable users to interact with the virtual environment 	<p>Solution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Virtual tour bus service utilizing the 5G network - Field-of-View Prediction-Assisted 360° Video Slicer to optimize resource consumption - Real-time interactivity and responsiveness in the virtual tour experience <p>Key Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of users - Average user engagement time - Customer satisfaction ratings and feedback - Number of partnerships with cultural institutions, tourism agencies, and education institutions - Cost per acquisition of new customers 	<p>Unique Value Proposition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seamlessly experience live bus tours remotely through high-quality virtual reality - Optimize network and computational resource consumption for a larger number of spectators - Real-time interactivity and responsiveness for an immersive tour experience - Enhanced user engagement and reach through immersive 5G-powered experiences 	<p>Unfair Advantage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exclusive partnerships with 5G network providers - Proprietary video slicing technology <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social media marketing - Partnerships with tourism agencies, cultural institutions, and education institutions - Content marketing - Direct sales and partnerships with hotels, travel agencies, and corporate clients 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tourists, travel agencies, hotels, individuals with accessibility needs, - Schools, universities, museums, cultural institutions - Local councils and municipalities - Event organizers <p>Early adopters</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tech-savvy individuals - Individuals with mobility limitations - Tourists seeking immersive experiences - Education institutions looking for innovative and engaging learning tools - Cultural institutions aiming to promote heritage and increase accessibility 		
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acquisition and maintenance of 5G network infrastructure - Marketing and advertising expenses - Partnership and collaboration costs (revenue sharing, joint marketing efforts) - Ongoing technical support and customer service - Operational costs (staffing, office space, utilities) 			<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Virtual tour ticket sales (individuals, group bookings) - Revenue sharing from Partnerships with tourism agencies, cultural institutions, and education institutions - Sponsored virtual tour experiences (brand collaborations, product placements) - Licensing the technology to other cities or organizations - In-app purchases (virtual souvenirs, additional content) 			
PRODUCT			MARKET			

Figure 16: Lean Canvas for UC3

In Figure 16 the lean canvas that has been developed for UC3 is presented.

4.4. UC4: AR content delivery for vehicular networks

This use case is about AR content delivery for future navigation systems of mobile users. Imagine a world where drivers could get real-time visual instructions transmitted to their windshield when navigating roads around the world. They could see virtual arrows pointing them in the correct direction, alerts letting them know about potential mechanical problems, and even receive notifications to help them drive more safely. The UC4 relies on AR capabilities of mobile devices and the edge computing capabilities in order to deliver AR content efficiently such as 3D objects and text.

4.4.1. Targeted market

Industrial companies with automated guided vehicles, automotive OEMs and mobile devices manufacturers.

4.4.2. Market assessment

The addition of AR to the navigation system in the motoring world is just one of the latest examples of how augmented reality could transform the way we drive in future. AR-enhanced navigation experiences are becoming increasingly popular as up-scale vehicle manufacturers look for new ways to lure wealthy end-users to their doors with more impressive tech. Several companies in the market will be able to integrate such an AR streaming application.

4.4.3. Stakeholders involved

The main internal stakeholders involved in this use case are the following:

- COGN (nApp developer)
- NOKIA (network provider)
- UBI-NXW (IANA platform)

The external stakeholders for UC4 are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Involved Stakeholders in UC4

Stakeholder	Role	Expected benefit
Mobile operator	AR streaming applications to mobile vehicular users	To provide a new service to the automotive vertical sector

4.4.4. Business Impact

UC4 can provide the addition of AR to the navigation system in the motoring world is just one of the latest examples of how augmented reality could transform the way we drive in future. AR-enhanced navigation experiences are becoming increasingly popular as up-scale vehicle manufacturers look for new ways to lure wealthy end-users to their doors with more impressive tech.

4.4.5. Main costs

The development of the actual user interface and the related AR content available to the edge server. The VNFs could be reused efficiently across the several AR user application versions.

4.4.6. Expected source of revenues

We are expecting to sale the full AR nApp for future in-vehicle applications.

4.4.7. Lean Canvas

Figure 17: Lean Canvas for UC4

4.5. Use Case 5: Real-time Road network risk-assessment

UC5 will develop a novel feature for the detection of hazardous driving events and risk assessment of road networks, combining aggregated data from an ML model trained on the edge with real-time driving behaviour data. In particular, the ML model will provide an overview of the average risk level of a road, based on the frequency of harsh events (harsh braking, harsh acceleration, speeding, mobile use). The UC will then employ 5G network capabilities for the detection of harsh events in real-time, thus warning users if there is an increase in risk level of the road segment due to more frequent occurrence of hazardous events.

4.5.1. Targeted market

The targeted market of UC5 is the insurtech and fintech market, where O7 is also currently active. In particular, the feature developed in UC5 will allow insurance companies to offer their clients who have a telematics contract this feature to increase their road safety. Insurance companies will benefit from UC5 via the reduction of accident rates, which will lead to a reduction in claims rates. Additionally, leasing companies can integrate the UC5 feature in their telematics offerings to increase the safety of drivers, decrease the chances of accident and so also increase the re-selling value of their vehicles (vehicles involved in accidents have lower re-selling values). The current O7 clientele includes insurance, leasing and fintech companies, so the UC5 feature can be streamlined in the market via the current O7 commercial channels.

4.5.2. Market assessment (competition, similar solutions)

The competitive advantage of the UC5 service lies in the fact that not V2V communication takes place. Rather, the communication takes place in a V2N manner (Vehicle-to-network), which means that one only needs a vehicle and the UC5 setup (smartphone + OBU) to run the service.

There are currently no similar solutions to any competitors offering telematics services that employ such a service, rendering the UC5 service even more attractive and unique.

4.5.3. Stakeholders involved

The main internal stakeholders involved in this use case are the following:

- NOKIA (Provider of Testbed/5G Network)
- UBI-NXW (Orchestration platform provider)

- LINKS (Provider of OBU with 5G connectivity)

The main external stakeholders involved in this use case are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Involved Stakeholders in UC5

Stakeholder	Role	Expected benefit
Insurance providers	Integration of the features in associated telematics products, and decrease of insurance costs (by decreasing risks involved)	Insurance providers could offer risk detection features to decrease improve driving behaviour, decrease insurance claims and cost, increase profitability. Further expected benefits include societal (e.g. decrease of road accidents, casualties, injuries) and eco (decrease of fuel consumption and CO2 emissions) benefits.
Public authorities	Use the developed features in “smart-city” projects	Public authorities pushing for transition of areas in “smart-areas”, can utilise the real-time risk detection feature to decrease the number of accidents on the road, increase the overall road safety and map the driving risk along road sections in order to optimize the budget utilization for the road network maintenance and improvements. Further expected benefits include societal (e.g. decrease of road accidents, casualties, injuries) and eco (decrease of fuel consumption and CO2 emissions) benefits.
Fleet management companies	Use feature in in-house or external telematics apps	Fleet management companies will improve the road safety of their fleet drivers, decrease the risk of road accidents for their fleets (and consequently decrease their insurance cost), and they will also decrease their maintenance and vehicle financing cost. Further expected benefits include societal (e.g. decrease of road accidents, casualties, injuries) and eco (decrease of fuel consumption and CO2 emissions) benefits.
Leasing, rental and Automotive companies	Integrate UC5 feature in telematics offerings.	Leasing, rental and Automotive companies will decrease the risk of road accidents for their fleets (and consequently decrease their insurance cost) and they will also decrease their maintenance and vehicle financing cost. Further expected benefits include societal (e.g. decrease of road accidents, casualties, injuries) and eco (decrease of fuel consumption and CO2 emissions) benefits.

4.5.4. Business impact

The developed feature will allow OSeven to enrich its solution (which at the moment is based on a post-trip assessment) with real-time components, creating new revenue streams and targeting new customer segments. Specifically, the developed feature will be targeted to a variety of stakeholders: insurance companies, public authorities, fleet management companies, rental and leasing companies. The identified stakeholders can profit from UC5 either by directly implementing the feature or by integrating it in their telematics offerings and will enable them to decrease insurance claims (insurance companies), the risk of road accidents (public authorities), and the damage done to vehicles through the reduction of accidents (fleet management, renting and leasing companies), while at the same time they increase user engagement.

UC5 will have a significant financial impact for OSeven and the above-mentioned stakeholders, as well as a significant societal and environmental impact. In fact, drivers utilising the UC5 feature will display a safer driving behaviour, as they will be alerted for potential risks, but at the same time this procedure will enhance driving awareness and training as a whole. This will decrease the number of road accidents, by avoiding crashes due to hazardous driving behaviour or low visibility conditions, and will also increase the overall road safety in the deployed area. Furthermore, it is a well-known fact that safe driving is also eco driving (safe driving may lead to a decrease in fuel consumption up to 30%). Therefore, the specific feature is expected to decrease significantly fuel consumption and CO2 emissions, which is a critical factor, especially in the light of the ongoing energy crisis.

4.5.5. Main costs

The impressive advantage of exploiting UC5 is that it only requires the 5G-IANA OBU and a smartphone to function. While the OBU can be hard to commercialize, it could be replaced via a virtual OBU that would run in the driver's smartphone, which is something that the UC5 partners have discussed and are currently exploring. This means that the entire functionality of UC5 would eventually only require the driver's smartphone to run, rendering the hardware costs null.

Currently, the OBU provided by LINKS in the 5G-IANA project which is the main hardware cost of UC5.

Other than hardware costs, the main costs of the UC5 service include:

- Engineering and production costs
- R&D costs

4.5.6. Expected sources of income

The expected sources of income after the commercialization of UC5 are the (i) the telematics contracts offered by insurance companies using the current O7 solution that will integrate UC5, (ii) the telematics contracts used by leasing and fleet management companies using the current O7 solution, and (iii) the contacts that could be signed with public authorities wishing to deploy the service of UC5 to increase awareness on road risk levels to drivers.

4.5.7. Lean Canvas

The lean canvas for UC5 is presented in Figure 18.

The Lean Canvas		UC5: Real-time road network risk assessment		29-05-2023
				Iteration #1
<p>Problem</p> <p>1) Real-time risk assessment while driving: increase driver awareness and visibility when driving, 2) Decrease of risk-level along road segments: a great societal problem - 44 road deaths per million inhabitants in 2021 in the EU translating to millions of € in claims</p> <p>Alternative Solutions</p> <p>No real-time risk assessment solutions today. The only meaningful way to decrease road accidents is to have better infrastructure, or improve driving behaviour.</p>	<p>Solution</p> <p>1) Real-time solution that functions in a V2N manner, 2) Device agnostic: only need for a specialized OBU which can be later substituted by a vOBU, 3) Personalized increase of road risk-level.</p> <p>Key Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users registered • Telematics contracts integrating the feature offered • Service availability and functionality 	<p>Unique Value Proposition</p> <p>The UC5 service will offer drivers a unique solution for assessing the road risk-level in real time and providing them with notifications in order to adjust their driving behaviour. This is a unique solution that will significantly increase the driver's awareness and visibility on the road, decrease their accident risk, and increase their overall driving safety.</p>	<p>Unfair Advantage</p> <p>No competitor currently offers such a solution that does not require V2V communication. This is made possible through the R&D activities of O7 and the 5G-IANA project.</p> <p>Channels</p> <p>After testing and improving, O7 will integrate the service in its current offering (once in TRL8+) and market it through its current sales pipeline.</p>	<p>Customer Segments</p> <p>Drivers (commercial, private), public authorities (that want to increase risk-level awareness to drivers), fleet management companies, leasing companies, insurance companies.</p> <p>Early adopters</p> <p>Insurance companies (will reduce claims costs), fleet management companies (will reduce accident risks and vehicle damage), leasing and rental companies (will reduce accident risk and increase vehicle value), public authorities (will reduce accident rates)</p>
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R&D costs • Engineering and Production costs • Distribution costs • Marketing (Customer Acquisition costs) 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <p>Insurance and fleet management telematics contracts</p> <p>OSeven currently has such a clientele and aims to streamline the UC5 service (once in TRL8+) via its current sales pipeline.</p>		
PRODUCT		MARKET		

Figure 18: Lean Canvas for UC5

4.6. UC6: Network Status Monitoring

UC6 provides an overview of the status of network components or virtual network functions and draws conclusions and predictions with respect to the performance of the monitored components. It utilizes V2X communications to deliver predictions of the network quality to a central computation entity at the Edge Server. This nApp has the goal to minimize the data collection effort through utilizing a distributed Machine Learning approach, i.e., instead of collecting large amounts of network monitoring data to be centrally analyzed, the ML analysis/prediction model is distributed on the VNFs located at the Far Edge. The goal of the ML model is (1) to learn data traffic patterns for data traffic prediction, (2) to learn network condition models to provide QoS predictions, and (3) to learn to distinguish between normal and abnormal network behaviors to detect and predict faults.

4.6.1. Targeted market

Industrial companies with automated guided vehicles, automotive OEMs.

4.6.2. Market assessment

The possibility to integrate the 5G networks into Autonomous driving solutions, implies the change to integrate the results in different markets and real contexts.

4.6.3. Stakeholders involved

In this UC the following internal stakeholders are involved:

- UULM (nApp provider)
- NOKIA (network provider)
- FSCOM (nApp provider)
- ICCS (nApp provider)

The external stakeholders around UC6 are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Involved stakeholders in UC6

Stakeholder	Role	Expected benefit
Insurance providers	Integration of the features in associated automotive applications, decrease of insurance costs (by decreasing risks involved)	Insurance providers could offer risk detection features to decrease improve driving behaviour, decrease insurance claims and cost, increase profitability.

Public authorities	Use the developed features in “smart-city” projects	Public authorities pushing for transition of areas in “smart-areas”, can utilise the real-time network behaviour to decrease the number of accidents on the road, increase the overall road safety and map the driving risk along road sections in order to optimize the budget utilization for the road network maintenance and improvements.
Fleet management companies	Use feature in in-house or external telematics apps	Fleet management companies will improve the road safety of their fleet drivers, decrease the risk of road accidents for their fleets .

4.6.4. Business Impact

UC6 can provide a valid outcome for all the partners involved because, it can be used by other UCs (like UC1 or UC3) to enhance their network efficiency and experience. The nApps developed and used in the UC6 will soon be available on the market, and in this case, we are able to obtain technological and business advantages.

4.6.5. Main costs

The main cost item will be related to the software developer tasks and for the neural learning training. In addition, we must take in consideration HW costs.

4.6.6. Expected source of revenues

Starting from the results, the revenues can be obtained for the sub-systems development. Could be possible use part of the project outcomes in prototypes and/or new autonomous driving solutions.

4.6.7. Lean Canvas

The Lean Canvas that has been developed for UC6 are presented in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Lean Canvas for UC6

4.7. UC7: Situational Awareness in Cross-Border Road Tunnel Accidents

UC7 focuses on providing situational awareness in a cross-border tunnel. Up to date, road tunnels, especially long ones, are already equipped with multiple devices installed in a tunnel providing situational awareness for road tunnel operators to certain extent. Situational awareness related data, collected in a road tunnel, are mainly available to the road tunnel operators only. This use case proposes idea of sharing situational awareness data with first responders whenever required (i.e., in case of an accident in the tunnel or in case of any other harmful event which requires intervention of first responders or any other authorized team) – even in case where first responders from different countries are intervening.

Closed/isolated communication systems of first responders (PPDR) on one end, and similarly isolated communication systems of tunnel operators on the other end is most common reality seen in the field today. UC7 therefore proposes utilizing 5G as a common communication system for all services required in a tunnel, i.e., daily operations as well

as operations in case of an incident. Using 5G for these purposes represent additional step in digitizing tunnel operations, as well as gives possibility to collect specific data from vehicles (C-V2X). Most importantly, 5G technology allows for data exchange among multiple stakeholders, including cross-border ones. Cross-border communication in PPDR (i.e., communication among PPDR teams from different countries), although already addressed by multiple projects, is mostly unavailable in the field today.

Another feature of the 5G ecosystem that PPDR vertical can benefit from in general, including this particular use case, is distributed infrastructure improving efficient data collection, storage, and processing. This also includes network automation features such as service creation, deployment, orchestration, reconfiguration, and scaling, to mention a few of them. Bottom line, the architecture based on 5G allows for flexible service life cycle management and may additionally also allow for better energy efficiency through distribution of service components along cloud continuum.

The use case itself does not primarily focus on what kind of data are, will be, or should be available in order to enhance situational awareness in case of tunnel operations, while it rather focuses on technical challenges related to the system architecture and software components required to realize the approach in practice. UC7 is therefore based on collecting data from a couple of environmental sensors integrated with Road-Side-Unit (RSU) and collecting data from vehicles through On-Board-Units (OBU). These data are forwarded to the analytics tools and further reported/represented to end-users (Tunnel Operations Control Centre, PSAP, First Responders) serving them for the specific goal of improving their situational awareness in the road tunnel. In terms of connectivity, the use case addresses connectivity related KPIs in terms of data collection and data distribution, having in mind specific QoS/QoE requirements. Cross-border dimension of the use case is represented by deploying service in two testbeds (one in Slovenia and the other in Germany) exploring PPDR related specifics, requirements and challenges of data exchange among the two separate testbeds/infrastructures. Finally, as mentioned previously, the UC7 also puts attention to 5G ecosystem's flexibility for service and network management.

4.7.1. Targeted market

The use case primarily addresses PPDR vertical/market, however, since it is focused to a specific environment, thus also partially targets road infrastructure and car/vehicle market.

In scope of the PPDR market, the UC7 targets road tunnel operators and PPDR teams responsible for intervening in road tunnel incidents. Especially the latter can significantly benefit of enhanced situational awareness provided by the solution presented. As suggested by the title of the UC, cross-border road tunnels are of special interest of the use case as well.

In terms of road tunnel infrastructure, UC7 contributors see market potential in providing 5G-enabled and orchestrated Road-Side Units and specific software for supporting various external sensors (including sensors based on legacy industrial standard communication protocols such as RS485 modbus), thus enabling road tunnel traffic control and management digitization based on 5G.

Another market potential is providing 5G-enabled and orchestrated OBUs and corresponding software supporting PPDR requirements which may include additional requirements set by vehicle manufacturer next to those required by the legislation.

4.7.2. Market assessment

Markets addressed (PPDR, road infrastructure, car market) are already matured market with established players, however, the ongoing digitization in all markets mentioned makes new opportunities for new players.

The primary focus of the UC7 is PPDR vertical where we can observe the market for 5G PPDR network and services is not yet fully established. In general, the market is well behind the innovations brought upon the evolution of communication networks. TETRA is used in many cases, while 5G is mainly limited to research efforts taking place, also noting EU-funded projects like Broadway and Broadmap represent strong initiative in the field. Otherwise, the concept of a 5G ecosystem and a vision for PPDR communication systems that may become less isolated as is today, seems interesting enough to attract various players. We can already see major 5G vendors taking steps towards PPDR market (Cisco, Ericsson, Huawei, Nokia, Samsung), vendors specialised in the security domain (Airbus, Thales, Motorola, Frequentis, Leonardo), mobile/ISP operators (e.g.: Telefonica, Vodafone), and European SMEs (e.g.: Athonet, Internet Institute, Nemergent).

Similar solutions on very limited scale are available as of today, i.e., providing only certain parts of the functionalities envisioned within the UC7. Complete and flexible solution as developed within the UC7 has not been identified on the market yet, while with further digitization and introducing 5G into road infrastructure and PPDR vertical, it is expected

for applications/services improving situational awareness to emerge as there seem to be a clear market potential for it.

4.7.3. Stakeholders involved

The solution proposed by the use case would involve multiple stakeholders when deployed in real life. Internal stakeholders already involved in UC7 are:

- TS, NOKIA (Mobile network operator)
- LINKS (HW and SW vendor, limited to providing RSU and OBU)
- ININ, LINKS (nApp developer)

External stakeholders, their respective roles and benefits can be found in Table 8.

Table 8: Involved Stakeholders in UC7

Stakeholder	Role	Expected benefit
Cloud infrastructure provider	Provides cloud and edge capabilities. This role can be also undertaken by MNO.	Providing new type of service which need to be designed to meet specific PPDR requirements.
Vehicle manufacturer (OEM)	OBU integrated in the vehicle provides vehicle related data relevant for the situational awareness.	Safety feature provides added value for the buyer as well as promotes responsibility towards other road tunnel users.
Road tunnel operator	User of the system.	Enables faster detection/prediction of (potential) accident and enables faster activation of first responders, thus mitigating potential damages caused by the accident.
PPDR community	User of the system.	Enables safer and more effective intervening in the tunnel due to additional data provided and due to communication possibilities with cross-border responders.
Road tunnel users (e.g., car drivers)	User of the system.	Safer use of the road tunnel.

4.7.4. Business Impact

As with many PPDR applications in general, business impact of the UC7 solution can be expressed in an in-direct way rather than in a direct way, i.e., increased level of security in the (cross-border) road tunnel. Enhanced situational awareness, gained by better connected sensorics, cannot fully prevent accident by itself, while it can primarily help mitigate the consequences of an accident by providing powerful tool to first responders.

Having in mind the use case addresses public road tunnels, the impact the solution may have targets the whole society as road transportation is of vital importance for mobility of people and goods.

4.7.5. Main costs

Traffic control systems for tunnels are mainly isolated systems which commonly comprise of video surveillance, various environmental sensors (smoke, CO, visibility, wind flow), smart traffic signs, lighting, fire extinguishing/hydrant system, ventilation, etc. Control of the complete system is usually performed by industrial control systems like SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition). Similarly to the process of migration to Industry 4.0 in industry vertical, it may be also expected for tunnel infrastructure to go similar way which would give opportunity for upgrading the existing systems with solutions like the one proposed by UC7. On the other end, we can also observe PPDR vertical is gradually migrating from isolated narrow-band system towards broadband systems based on mobile technologies such as 5G enabling also cross-border connectivity. When migrations on both ends are complete, the deployment of the UC7-like solution is straightforward requiring merely deployment of software components only. In case 5G capabilities are not available at any side, or at one side only, additional efforts and cost related to infrastructure deployment and integration is required.

4.7.6. Expected source of revenues

Revenues are expected from selling the end product (hardware and software components) or from selling services (connectivity, edge and cloud capabilities, situational awareness services). The decision will depend on current market needs and certain HW/SW/nApp provider's business plan. Additionally, HW and SW developers contributing to UC7 may also sell licenses of their particular product(s) to third parties, e.g., to infrastructure providers/integrators in order to be integrated into their "tunnel control applications".

4.7.7. Lean Canvas

The Lean Canvas that has been created for UC7 is presented in Figure 20.

The Lean Canvas

UC7 – Situational awareness in Cross-Border Road Tunnel Accidents

29-05-2023

Iteration #1

Problem <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data sharing among different domains (PPDR and Road Infrastructure Operators) in different countries - Collect additional data related to traffic/security in the road tunnel - Resource optimization and fast deployment of new functionalities 		Solution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 5G based solution - Distributed architecture (cloud continuum) - QoS/QoE assured solution - nApp approach 		Unique Value Proposition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - users have clear understanding of the situation in the road tunnel - situational awareness data are available everywhere 		Unfair Advantage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - first responders have direct insight to the situation in the tunnel and can choose perspective angle as they find optimally 		Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - first responders - road tunnel operators - road tunnel infrastructure providers - MNOs - service providers 	
Alternative Solutions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Isolated proprietary networks with limited capabilities of data sharing 		Key Metrics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - QoS KPIs (data throughput, RTT, reliability, jitter) - cross-border connectivity - service deployment and scale-out time - vendor agnostics 				Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - existing business partners: PPDR vertical, MNOs, service providers, cloud providers - "Road Tunnel Safety" community 		Early adopters Road tunnels in phase of renovating safety/security infrastructure	
Cost Structure Development Hosting HW costs Connectivity Payroll					Revenue Streams Product license sell End-product sell Providing/operating service				
PRODUCT					MARKET				

Figure 20: Lean Canvas for UC7

5. CONCLUSION

This deliverable has presented the work implemented in *T6.3: Sustainable business models* until M24. The challenges regarding the 5G service provisioning have been presented. There are several issues that must be solved with the most crucial that of the deployment of the 5G networks in a way that they can offer services without interruption within a country or when crossing borders. The different value networks that have been identified show that, currently, MNOs continue to have a dominant place within the ecosystem as in most of the countries they are the only owners of spectrum. Collaboration among the different actors increases the value of all participants in the ecosystem and acts as a model that must be examined by all stakeholders.

More details about the services that the 5G-IANA platform can offer have been also presented. The main service is the experimentation, while also value-added services like training and consulting can be built on top. Details about the foreseen cost structure have been provided. All this information will be used for the rest of the activities of T6.3 that has to do with the sustainability of the 5G-IANA AOEP. The final results including a business plan will be presented in D6.4, considering any feedback received by the participants of the Open Call.

The first iteration of the business models around the seven 5G-IANA UCs is also presented, covering aspects related to targeted market they are addressing and providing an overview of the current market trends and main competitors. In addition, the main stakeholders involved now and in the future for each of the UC are presented along with the main costs and type of revenues. For all UCs, a lean canvas has been developed providing details about the envisioned business model; these models will also be fine-tuned, and their final iterations will be presented in D6.4.

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